

Double Trouble: Understanding risks from invasive species and climate change

Summary: Individually, invasive species and climate change are major threats to global ecosystems. Together they create new challenges for effective management. Management strategies need to be designed to respond to this double trouble, and we need to understand how these two forms of global change interact.

All regions are likely to see interactions between invasive species and climate change. The North Central region is particularly vulnerable for the following reasons:

- Northerly latitudes are warming more than southerly latitudes, leading to more rapid environmental changes
- Southerly invasive species are shifting their ranges north, and low-elevation invasives are moving upwards
- Some of the North Central's key ecosystems are particularly at risk when climate change is combined with invasion
 - Sagebrush and forest ecosystems can experience a grass-fire cycle with invasive grasses
 - Climate change can make wetland habitats (e.g. prairie potholes) more suitable for invasive species

Management Options

- Monitor for early detection of new invasive species that have moved into the region
 - A place to start: <https://www.invasivespeciesinfo.gov/subject/lists>
- Look for alternative management strategies if pesticides become less effective
- Keep the timing of management flexible to respond to climate variability, extreme events, and differences in invasive phenologies
- Explore methods to more effectively limit new invasive species introduction

Figure 1: Major interactions between non-native invasive species and climate change.

Climate extremes create opportunities for invasion

- Extreme droughts, fires, and floods create novel disturbances and opportunities for invasion
- Drought stress increases tree vulnerability to invasive pests

Cheatgrass takes advantage of extremes and contributes to future fire.

Invasives shift their ranges into new ecosystems

- Invasive plants and aquatics are often native to warmer regions, making them preadapted to climate warming in new regions
- New animal pests, pathogens, and 86 invasive plants are expected to move into the North Central region (2040-2060)

Purple starthistles and Japanese beetles are moving northward.

Invasives become more competitive

- Warming and elevated CO₂ cause invasive plants to grow faster and produce more biomass than native plants
- Invasive species often have traits that help them adapt to new and changing environments (e.g. broad environmental tolerances, rapid growth rates)

(Invasive) Common carp spawn after disturbances before other species arrive.

Shifting seasons / Phenology

- Milder winters increase pest survival
- Invasive plants may have different timing of major life events (e.g. germination, flowering), giving them an advantage in a longer growing season

Purple loosestrife may outcompete native rockcress due to the longer available growing season and greater seed production.

Herbicides/Pesticides become less effective

- Rising CO₂ leads to increased weed biomass (particularly roots), making chemical treatments less effective
- Temperature, CO₂, and water availability interact with pesticides, with a net negative impact on efficacy under climate change

Canada Thistle is harder to kill via herbicide with higher CO₂.

New introduction pathways

- Human activities that introduce non-native species are likely to move / increase under climate change (e.g. agriculture, recreation, construction)
- Altered streamflows and flood regimes may facilitate dispersal of non-native species

Zebra mussel spread may benefit from new pathways.

Allen & Bradley 2016 Biol. Conserv.; Bajer & Sorensen Biol. Invasions 2010; Bradley et al. 2010 Biol. Invasions; Bradley et al. 2015 Frontiers Ecol. Evol; Calinger et al 2013 Eco Letters; Colautti et al 2017 Bio. Sci.; DeKeyser et al 2013 Nat Areas; Dukes et al. 2009 Can J. For. Res.; EDDMaps <https://www.eddmaps.org/>; Finch et al 2021 IS in For Range of US; Hand et al 2018 USDA FS; King et al 2015 Eco. Model.; Kistner-Thomas 2019 J. Ins. Sci; Kolb et al. 2016 For. Ecol. Mgmt.; Korres et al. 2016 Agronomy for Sust. Dev.; Liu et al. 2017 Global Change Biol.; Matzrafi 2018 Pest Man Sci; **NE RISCC 2019**; Pyke et al. 2008 Cons. Biol.; Rahel & Olden 2008 Cons. Biol.; Rosenzweig et al 2001 Glob. Chan. & Hum. Health; **USGS 2019**; Varanasi et al 2016 Adv in Ag; Ziska et al. 2004 Weed Science

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